

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	02	11	Punta Arenas	S 53	10.500	W 70	54.100
End	2021	03	18	Puerto Montt	S 41	28.000	W 72	53.000

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

The objective of this stage was to carry out three transects from the head of the fjord to the open sea, in the archipelago of Patagonia. In each transect, the objective was to carry out 5 oceanographic stations for the collection of seawater samples (genomics, transcriptomics, nutrients, pH, TA, DOC, POC, pigments, etc.), in situ measurements and seston sampling. Including measurements of surface water with high temporal resolution of temperature, optical and chemical variables (salinity, pH, pCO₂)

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin HERTAU
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Nicolas BIN
3	CREW -	David MONMARCHE
4	CREW -	François AURAT
5	CREW -	Loïc CAUDAN
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie BIN
7	CREW - Media	Maeva BARDY
8	GUEST	Marcello SANCHEZ ALCAZAR
9	GUEST	Enrique
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Miguel MOLL
11	SCIENCE - B - Chief Scientist	Rodrigo TORRES
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Céline DIMIER
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Douglas COUET
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Milena CERDA
15	SCIENCE -	

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The studied environment corresponds to a fjord system, which involves a strong east-west salinity gradient, product of the high precipitation on the west side of the Andes and the net melting of the continental ice fields.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

We revert the decision of the General Staff that prohibited work in the interior fjords and the collection of temperature and salinity data in the Magallanes region. 11 planned stations and 4 initially unplanned CTD stations were carried out (authorized by request sent when we were in the Strait of Magellan). Preliminary results show that the selected stations represent well the coast-ocean gradients and therefore are a representative sample of the habitat variety of the subantarctic coastal sea. For example strong E-W gradients of salinity, CDOM and turbidity

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide overview of sampling activities during the Campaign.

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	CAST – Z00-Z10	CAST – Z00-D1	NET – WPII 20 - Horizontal	NET – WPII 20 - vertical	NET – WPII 200 - Horizontal	NET – WPII 200 - Vertical	CAST – Z00-D2	CAST – Z00+Z01+Z05	Bow Pole	Microtops	HTSRB	NET – Manta 330	CAST – Z01+Z03+Z05	NET – Régent 680	NET – Régent 680	CAST – Z02+Z04+Z06	Rodrigo' s net 300 – 150 - 0m	Rodrigo' s net 300 – 50 - 0m	CAST – Z07	CAST – Z08	CAST – Z09	CAST – Z10	
001	20210220	50° 53.9	74° 16.7	x	x	X	x	x	x		x				x	x	x	X		X						
002	20210222	50° 42.1	74° 34.4	x	x	X	x	x	x		X	x			x	x	X	X		x	x					
003	20210224	50° 34.007	74° 48.093	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					
005	20210226	50°28.3	76°11.8	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x	X	X	X	X	X
	20210226	50°28.566	75°57.717																	x						
	20210226	50°27.608	75°21.336									x														
004	20210228	50°30.11	75°00.9	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					
006	20210303	48°08.2	73°28.1	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					
007	20210305	47°59.1	73°47.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					
008	20210306	47°46.05	74°36.41	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					
009	20210314	41°51.926	73°14.778	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X				X	X	X	X		X	x					
	20210314	41°55.24	73°03.89									x														
010	20210315	41°44.50	72°42.47	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x					

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

Will be re-structured once we get a few inventories.

Storage T°C	+10	+10	+10	+4	+4	+4	-20	-20	-20	-80	-80	-80
Box size										#1	#2	#3
Chemical												

Protocol	Container type												
AI	petri-slide	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AS	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	0
SP300	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	54	0
MP300	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
CP300	petri-slide	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CP300	Zip-lock	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MTE-S	125-mL Bottle	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HP	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	136	0
DOC	amber vial	0	0	0	0	0	58	0	0	0	0	0	0
PM	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58
ETS	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	66
eDNA-EC	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
eDNA-EC	culture-tube	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
eDNA	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0
GHG	100-mL-vial	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TA	500-mL-bottle	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NU	20-mL-vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	0	0	0
S20	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	0
E20	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0
FM20	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S200	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	0
E200	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0
F200	250-mL-bottle	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PM300	20-80-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0
S680	petri-plates	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0
E680	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0
F680	250-mL-bottle	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TXNA	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0
TXCO	50-mL-falsom	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TXCOdry	petri-slide	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TXMP	50-mL-falsom	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TXCY	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0
HG	125-mL-bottle	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EM	petri-slide	48	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SG	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0
FC	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	144	0
S320	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	111	0	0

